

Quantum Dynamical Probability Of Space and Time?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 19, 2025

In (1), we argued that in terms of conservation, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ functioned in the same way as a quantum dynamical probability $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(i p \cdot r)$. The difference, as we noted, is that $p(e_i)$ is a real number and so indicates a probability beyond conservation/unknown outcome pairs (i.e. $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T)$ if $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$). In particular, it indicates that there is an uncertainty in energy for a particle given by $p(e_i)$.

In the quantum case, $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ are complex, but have a unit modulus for all free particles. Thus, even though conservation of energy and momentum are enforced, as in the MB case and there is uncertainty in outcome pairs, one may ask: Where is the uncertainty linked with probability of a free particle? We argue that it is in the space and time variables, $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta p = \hbar/x$ (one dimension). In other words, there should be some uncertainty associated with a probability and we argue that this uncertainty is not in E and p for a free particle, but rather in space and time, but governed by E and p .

We further note that in the MB case and quantum cases, the Shannon's entropy function mimics the energy or momentum constraint and this carries over to the quantum free particle case.

Probability and Uncertainty

It seems that probability is linked with some kind of uncertainty in a problem. If there is no uncertainty, then there is no reason to have a probability, we argue. In case of a toss of a die or coin (uniform distribution), the uncertainty is in the outcome. In the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann ideal gas particle, the uncertainty is in the energy, i.e. $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. In such cases, there is one variable on which the probability depends and this is the uncertainty variable.

Quantum Free Particle Probability

A free particle is deterministic and has a fixed E (energy) and p (momentum). We suggest that it is nevertheless associated with a dynamical probability which ensures that there is conservation of momentum and energy with equal probability for any outcome pairs which satisfy conservation. We first note that the MB distribution is also associated with conservation of energy, i.e.

$$\exp(-e_1/T) \exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T) \text{ if } e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \quad ((1))$$

Thus, there is both a sense of uncertainty (not knowing the particle's energy), but once it is known, a sense of conservation, which, in turn, is linked with a second kind of uncertainty, namely the (e_3, e_4) outcome pair as shown in ((1)). Any e_i, e_j pair has the same probability, given $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$. Thus, uncertainty exists at the level of single e value, but also among e_i, e_j pairs, but these, in turn, are linked to a conservation law.

For a quantum free particle, conservation of energy or momentum is based on deterministic, known values. There is no uncertainty in the value of p or E for the free particle. Nevertheless, there is uncertainty in e_i , e_j or p_{xi} , p_{xj} pair values linked with conservation. We proposed that one should have:

$$\text{Dynamical probability } \exp(-iEt) \text{ and } \exp(i p_x x), \exp(i p_y y), \exp(i p_z z) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) complies with uncertainty in pairs of E_i , E_j or p_{xi} , p_{xj} (etc) which are directly linked to conservation as in ((1)), but now for E and p , i.e.

$$\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i p_3 x) \exp(i p_4 x) \text{ if } p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \quad ((3))$$

The question we then ask is: Where is the inherent uncertainty for $\exp(-iEt)$ or $\exp(-i p_x x)$ by itself (ignoring conservation and pairs)? $\exp(-i p_x x)$ and $\exp(-i E t)$ are probabilities and so should be associated with an inherent uncertainty.

Given that E and p are exactly known, we suggest that the uncertainty is within the period and wavelength, i.e. within space and time:

$$\Delta t = \hbar/E \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x = \hbar/p \quad ((4b)) \quad \text{one-dimension}$$

This uncertainty has physical consequences as seen in 2-slit experiments and other interference/diffraction situations.

It seems, however, that there is possibly a bigger issue present.

Probability As a Lack of Details

It is sometimes said that one introduces probability into a deterministic scenario to account for information one does not want to capture. For example, if a person tosses a coin, a film showing every detail of the toss might allow one to predict that a particular toss will be heads or tails. In such a case, probability is a kind of “throw away the details” approach to dealing with a problem. We argue, however, that even if one can predict the outcome of a particular toss, one has no idea what an outcome will be, just before a toss, unless there is bias in the system. Thus, the idea of probability or uncertainty seems to be inherent. It is possible that accounting for details may allow for a single toss prediction, but not for the details and outcome of the next toss. Thus, probability does not seem to be a “throw away the details” situation. There seems to be genuine uncertainty in a system. In the case of particles in an ideal gas, one might argue that one could deterministically know the initial conditions of each and technically predict all collisions exactly. This does not change the fact that if there is no bias in the system, one must have the result:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \quad e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \quad ((5))$$

if equilibrium is reached.

In the quantum case, the uncertainty is actually linked to space and time which seems to show the importance of probability and its consequences. One does not simply use $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(ipx)$ as probability for convenience, but there are actually associated uncertainties in time and space. The fact that there is probability in the first place is due to the unknown outcome pairs E_i, E_j or p_{xi}, p_{xj} , but this has implications for a single member of the pair. The implications are not at the p or E level, but at the level of a x or t which are factors of p and E needed to make probability invariant under frame changes. Thus, uncertainty over outcome pairs leads directly to uncertainty in space and time.

Furthermore, for a quantum particle, one cannot argue that given enough details one knows exactly the outcome pairs. Thus, quantum particles are inherently probabilistic (uncertain) and this carries over to classical particles, although given the tiny wavelengths and frequencies, these uncertainties may be too small to be measured.

Entropy

We consider the idea of Shannon's entropy for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. We have argued in previous notes that entropy is really a consequence of the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$, in fact, it has the same mathematical form. The fact that one sums over energies, shows that the uncertainty is in the energy of the particle. We have argued that one may create a function:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) \text{ such that } h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ and } p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i) \quad ((6))$$

yields $-E_{ave}/T$ to first order if one uses the differentials of the constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \rightarrow \sum_i dp(i) = 0 \text{ and } \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \rightarrow \sum_i e_i dp(i) = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Then: $p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i) = 1$ and one obtains: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ which ensures equal probability for any e_i, e_j pair such that $e_i + e_j = E_1$, where E_1 is some number.

One may try to apply the same approach to quantum free particles and write a constraint:

$$\sum_i x_i p(p_{xi}) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) seems to imply that x_i must be the uncertain variable, because p is a fixed number. Then one may vary (i.e. vary x_i)

$$p(i) \ln(p(i)) \rightarrow dp(i) \ln(p(i)) + dp(i) \quad ((9))$$

If one normalizes $p(x_i)$ over some length L , then there is a second constraint: $\int dx p(xp)$. Thus, the math becomes the same as for the MB case and one obtains $\exp(i px)$ as a solution. In other words, x_i is uncertain in the quantum free case (for px), just as y is uncertain for py etc and t for E . This uncertainty is as real as the uncertainty of e_i in the MB case. In the MB case, however, there is a fixed total energy which is distributed among particles and so it is

the distribution which leads to the probability. In the quantum free particle case, there is no distribution of space and time, yet there is an uncertainty in them due to the value of E and p . Thus, this uncertainty changes with E and p and shows that space-time is somehow linked with energy and momentum, at least in terms of uncertainty and probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a probability must be associated with an uncertainty. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $p(e_i)$ means that there is an uncertainty in the energy that a single particle may have. In other words, there is a total energy E which is distributed over N particles. There is a second uncertainty in the MB case, due to conservation. Any e_i, e_j outcome pair has the same product probability $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ as $p(e_1)p(e_2)$ for the incoming e_1 and e_2 particles if $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$.

In the quantum free particle case, we argue that this same outcome uncertainty exists for energy and momentum and propose the dynamical probabilities: $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(i p x)$ etc. The point we make is that these must also have an inherent uncertainty not associated with a product of probabilities. We suggest that this uncertainty is actually in time and space, $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ (one dimension), but is directly linked to the E and p values. In other words, probability does not simply seem to be used to bypass details in the quantum case, but implies direct effects on behaviour in space and time (i.e. interference). Furthermore, the notion of equal probability for various outcome pairs linked to the same conservation value implies that each member of the pair must be linked to an intrinsic uncertainty. In the free particle case, it is not a probability linked with p or E (the conservation variables), but with space and time, variables needed to make the probability expression invariant under changes of frame, i.e. $-Et + p \cdot r$ is a Lorentz invariant.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Probability Related to Conservation of Energy/Momentum and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2025)